

JEEVANIYA GAṆA: A REVIEW BASED ON CLASSICAL TEXTS AND MODERN EVIDENCE

*¹Dr. Khusboo Kumari Gupta, ²Dr. Parminder Kumar Moudgil

¹Department of Dravyaguna, Assistant Professor, Krishna Ayurved Medical College, Vadodara.

²MD (Gold Medalist), PhD Ayurveda, Guide, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh

Article Received on 21 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 11 Jan. 2026,
Article Published on 01 Feb. 2026,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18494160>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Khusboo Kumari Gupta

Department of Dravyaguna, Assistant Professor, Krishna Ayurved Medical College, Vadodara.

How to cite this Article: *¹Dr. Khusboo Kumari Gupta, ²Dr. Parminder Kumar Moudgil (2026). Jeevaniya Gaṇa: A Review Based On Classical Texts And Modern Evidence. "World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(3), 1964–1968.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Jeevaniya gana is a group of Ayurvedic medicinal plants extensively described for their Jīvanīya, Bṛmhaṇa, Balya, and Rasāyana properties by Acharya Vagbhatt. These drugs are predominantly Madhura in rasa and Śīta in vīrya, they are especially useful in conditions like tissue depletion, general debility, and reduced vitality. Classical Ayurvedic texts such as Charaka Saṃhitā and Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya provide detailed references regarding their therapeutic applications, particularly in Rasāyana and Vājīkaraṇa karma.^[1] The present review study aims to compile and critically analyze classical descriptions of Jeevaniya gana and correlate them with accepted botanical identities, and interpret their pharmacological actions viewed through the lens of modern studies.

KEYWORDS: Jeevaniya Gana, Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya, Rasāyana Karma, Jeevaniya.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, Acharyas have classified dravyas into various Gaṇas based on the similarities in their therapeutic action, pharmacological properties and clinical indications. Among these, Jeevaniya gana has a prominent place due to its potent nourishing, rejuvenating, and life-sustaining properties. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya emphasizes its clinical utility in Rasāyana and Vājīkaraṇa therapies, these drugs are indicated in improving vitality, immunity, and

reproductive health.^[2,3] All the dravyas of Jeevaniya Gaṇa are noted for their ability to support tissue nourishment (dhātu-puṣṭi), enhance ojas, and restore physiological equilibrium without causing imbalances in doṣas. Nowadays, the increasing scarcity of authentic raw drugs, coupled with widespread substitution and adulteration, threatens the efficacy and reliability of Jeevaniya gana formulations. This highlights the need for a comprehensive classical review of jeevaniya gana dravya of Astanga hridaya that blends traditional textual knowledge, botanical identification, and modern pharmacological validation, ensuring the therapeutic authenticity and safe clinical application of this important.^[4-6,8]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present work is a **literary review** based on classical Ayurvedic texts and research articles

Sources of Data

- Aṣṭāṅga Hr̥daya
- Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API), Part I
- CCRAS publications on Rasāyana drugs
- Peer-reviewed journals

METHODOLOGY

Classical references of Jeevaniya gana were identified, analyzed, and systematically arranged. Botanical correlations were adopted from API, Charak samhita & Astanga Hr̥daya. Modern pharmacological findings were reviewed to establish scientific correlation.

Composition of Jeevaniya Gana (Group of Restoratives)

जीव ती काकोयौ मेदे दवे मुदगमाषप य च ।

ऋषभकजीवकमधुकं चेत गणो जीवनीया यः ॥ (A.H.SU.15/8)

S. No.	Sanskrit Name	Botanical Name	Family	Part Used
1.	Jīvantī	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i>	Asclepiadaceae	Root
2.	Kākolī	<i>Roscoea procera</i>	Zingiberaceae	Root
3.	Kṣīrakākolī	<i>Lilium polyphyllum</i>	Liliaceae	Root
4.	Medā	<i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i>	Liliaceae	Rhizome
5.	Mahāmedā	<i>Polygonatum cirrhifolium</i>	Liliaceae	Rhizome
6.	Mudgaparṇī	<i>Phaseolus trilobus</i>	Fabaceae	Panchāṅga
7.	Māṣaparnī	<i>Teramnus labialis</i>	Fabaceae	Root & Panchāṅga
8.	Jīvaka	<i>Malaxis acuminata</i>	Orchidaceae	Tuber
9.	Rṣabhaka	<i>Microstylis muscifera</i>	Orchidaceae	Tuber
10.	Madhuka (Yaṣṭimadhu)	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Fabaceae	Root & Stolon

Rasa-Pañcaka and Pharmacological Actions- Rasa- Madhura**Guna-** Guru and Snigdha,**Vīrya-** Sita**Vipāka-** Madhura**Karma-** Jīvanīya, Bṛmhaṇa, Balya, Rasāyana, Vṛṣya, Ojavardhaka**Therapeutic Indications-** Dhātu-kṣaya, Karśya (emaciation), Kṣaya, Śoṣa, Vājīkaraṇa therapy, Pediatric and geriatric Rasāyana.^[1-3]**Modern Pharmacology and Recent Scientific Studies**

Recent studies provide scientific support to the classical claims of Kākolyādi Gaṇa. Several constituent drugs exhibit antioxidant, immunomodulatory, adaptogenic, anti-inflammatory, and anabolic activities.^[8-12]

Polygonatum species (**Medā and Mahāmedā**) has anti-fatigue and anabolic effects, validating their Bṛmhaṇīya karma.^[9]

Glycyrrhiza glabra (**Madhuka/Yastimadhu**) shows anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties.^[8]

Mudgaparṇī and *Māṣaparṇī* improve nutritional status and enhance immune response.^[10]

Leptadenia reticulata (**Jīvantī**) exhibits rejuvenative and adaptogenic properties, supporting its Rasāyana property.^[11]

The above finding shows close relation between Ayurvedic karma and modern pharmacological observations.

DISCUSSION

The dravyas of Jeevaniya gana represents a unique therapeutic group in Ayurveda, mainly indicated for nourishment, rejuvenation, and enhancement of vitality. The collective pharmacodynamic action of its constituent drugs plays a significant role in supporting the formation and sustenance of all sapta dhātu, thereby improving overall strength and endurance.

Classical descriptions highlight the predominance of Madhura rasa, Guru–Snigdha guṇa, and Śīta vīrya, which together promote anabolic processes and stabilization of physiological

functions without causing undue provocation of doṣas.^[2]

As per the classical texts, the properties of Jeevaniya gana contribute directly to enhancement of ojas, which is regarded as the essence of all dhātus and the foundation of immunity and vitality.^[1] Unlike drugs that exert aggressive or stimulatory effects, Jeevaniya gana acts gently by improving nutrient assimilation and dhātu-puṣṭi, thereby ensuring sustained physiological balance. This explains its repeated recommendation in Rasāyana and Vājīkaraṇa therapies, especially for pediatric, geriatric, and chronically debilitated individuals.^[2,3]

Experimental and clinical studies conducted on individual drugs of Jeevaniya gana demonstrate antioxidant, immunomodulatory, adaptogenic, and anti-inflammatory activities.^[8-11] Such findings provide a rational scientific explanation for the Rasāyana concept described in Ayurvedic texts. The anabolic and anti-fatigue effects observed in certain constituent plants support their traditional use in improving strength, muscle mass, and recovery from illness.^[9,10] The convergence of classical theory with modern pharmacological evidence strengthens the relevance of Jeevaniya ganain integrative healthcare practices.^[8,12]

Despite its well-established therapeutic importance, the practical application of Jeevaniya gana faces several challenges. Many drugs of this gana are botanically rare and geographically restricted, leading to issues related to procurability and authenticity of genuine drugs. This scarcity & has encouraged substitution and adulteration of drugs, which may compromise therapeutic efficacy and safety.^[4] Additionally, lack of uniform standards for identification, processing, and quality control further complicates clinical utilization.^[5,6] These concerns highlight the urgent need for conservation strategies, cultivation programs, and pharmacopeial standardization.

CONCLUSION

Here, the drugs of Jeevaniya gana represents a keystone of Rasāyana and Bṛiṃhaṇa therapy in Ayurveda, these dravyas are renowned for its ability to nourish the sapta dhātus, enhancing ojas and promotes overall vitality and health. Acharya Vagbhatt, highlights its role in restoring strength of individual, supports tissue regeneration and maintaining physiological balance, particularly in debilitated, convalescent, and geriatric individuals. Modern pharmacological studies further proves these traditional claims, demonstrating its

adaptogenic, antioxidant, immunomodulatory and anabolic activities. To ensure its continued clinical relevance, we must employ integrated research, combining textual study, pharmacognostical authentication, scientific standardization and conservation of the authentic raw drugs. Such efforts would preserve the therapeutic integrity of Jeevaniya gana while enabling its evidence-based application in contemporary healthcare systems.

REFERENCES

1. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita with Chakrapani commentary. Sutrasthana, Chapter 4. Varanasi Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series Office.
2. Vagbhata. *Ashtanga Hridaya* with Arunadatta commentary. Sutrasthana, Chapter 15. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan.
3. Vagbhata. *Ashtanga Hridaya*. Uttarasthana (Rasayana Adhyaya). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan.
4. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. Part I, Vols. I–VI. New Delhi: Ministry of AYUSH, Government of India.
5. Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences. *Rasayana Therapy in Ayurveda*. New Delhi: CCRAS.
6. Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences. *Scientific Validation of Rasayana Drugs*. New Delhi: CCRAS.
7. Sharma RK, Dash B. *Materia Medica of Ayurveda*. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series Office.
8. Thatte UM, Dahanukar SA. Rasayana concept: Clues from immunomodulatory therapy. *Indian J Pharmacol*.
9. Patwardhan B, Gautam M. Botanical adaptogens in traditional medicine. *J Ayurveda Integr Med*.
10. Pandey MM, Rastogi S, Rawat AKS. Indian traditional Ayurvedic system of medicine and nutritional supplementation. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*.
11. Anonymous. Rasayana drugs and their role as adaptogens. *AYU*.
12. Anonymous. Review articles on Rasayana and adaptogenic drugs. *Int J Ayurveda Pharm Res*.